

SOCIO-EMOTIONAL WELL-BEING OF YOUNG LEARNERS EXPOSED TO SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS: A CASE STUDY ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, the proliferation of social media platforms has significantly influenced various aspects of individuals' lives, including the socio-emotional well-being of young learners. As digital natives, young learners are increasingly exposed to social media platforms from an early age, shaping their interactions, perceptions, and behaviors both online and offline. This qualitative multiple-case study aimed to explore the socio-emotional well-being of young learners exposed to social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2024-2025. The study involved 15 teachers who met the inclusion criteria and utilized semi-structured interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) as research instruments. Data analysis employed a thematic approach to examine participants' insights. The findings revealed that social media significantly impacts young learners' socio-emotional development, offering both benefits and risks. Positive aspects include fostering social connections, self-expression, and emotional support, while negative effects involve cyberbullying, social comparison, addiction, and mental health issues. Coping strategies such as open communication, setting boundaries, and developing digital literacy emerged as key to mitigating the adverse effects. The study emphasizes the importance of digital literacy programs, parental guidance, and the promotion of healthy online habits to safeguard young learners' emotional well-being. Recommendations include integrating digital literacy and social-emotional learning into the curriculum, providing teacher training on digital well-being, and promoting parental involvement. Additionally, future research should explore the effectiveness of digital literacy programs and investigate how parental guidance

influences children's social media usage. In conclusion, while social media presents challenges, its responsible use, supported by education and guidance, can significantly enhance young learners' socio-emotional growth and development.

Keywords: *socio-emotional well-being, young learners, social media platforms*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

In recent years, the proliferation of social media platforms has significantly influenced various aspects of individuals' lives, including the socio-emotional well-being of young learners. As digital natives, young learners are increasingly exposed to social media platforms from an early age, shaping their interactions, perceptions, and behaviors both online and offline. Understanding the impact of social media exposure on the socio-emotional well-being of young learners is crucial for educators, policymakers, and parents to effectively support their holistic development.

Social media platforms have become integral parts of the lives of young learners, offering opportunities for communication, connection, and self-expression (Bestet al. 2014). However, alongside the benefits, concerns have been raised regarding the potential negative effects of social media use on young learners' socio-emotional well-being. Research suggests that excessive use of social media may contribute to feelings of loneliness, anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem among young users (Primack et al., 2017; Twenge & Campbell, 2018).

Despite growing interest in the topic, there remains a significant research gap regarding the socio-emotional well-being of young learners exposed to social media platforms, particularly in international and Philippine settings. Existing studies have predominantly focused on adult populations or adolescents, overlooking the unique experiences and vulnerabilities of younger children in the digital age (Livingstone et al. 2018). Moreover, while some research has explored the effects of social media on adolescents' mental health, less attention has been paid to the socio-emotional well-being of young learners in elementary and primary school settings (Viner et al., 2019).

Furthermore, existing literature on social media and children's well-being often lacks contextualization within the Philippine setting. Given the cultural diversity and socioeconomic disparities in the Philippines, it is essential to examine how social media use influences the socio-emotional well-being of young learners in this context.

By addressing these research gaps, this study seeks to explore the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat.

Research Questions

This research explored the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, this study addressed the following research questions:

1. How do young learners perceive their socio-emotional well-being in relation to their experiences and interactions on social media platforms?
2. What are the specific socio-emotional challenges faced by young learners as a result of their exposure to social media platforms?
3. How do young learners cope with the challenges they encountered?
4. What are the potential benefits of social media platform use for the socio-emotional development of young learners, and how do these benefits manifest in their daily lives?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, a qualitative research, specifically the a multiple-case study, was employed to explore deeply the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025.

Case studies allow researchers to gain a deep and comprehensive understanding of complex issues. They provide detailed insights into the contextual factors that influence the subject being studied. This level of depth is often unattainable through other research methods such as surveys or experiments (Ngag, 2023).

Respondents of the Study

Table 1 displays the participants' qualifications, as determined by the criteria established by the researcher before selecting eligible informants for the study. With a smaller number of cases, researchers can conduct a more in-depth and detailed analysis of each case. This allows for a richer exploration of the complexities, contexts, and unique characteristics of each participant or case, which is essential in qualitative research (Doluran & Ngag, 2024). The study involved a total of 15 teachers in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria:

Table 1. Participants' Inclusion Criteria

Criteria Description	Criteria Description
Teaching Experience in Handling Young Learners	Teachers must have at least two years of experience handling young learners (elementary or early secondary levels) to provide insights into their socio-emotional well-being related to social media exposure.
Familiarity with Students' Social Media Engagement	Participants should have observed or engaged in discussions about students' social media use and its effects on their socio-emotional development, either through classroom interactions or counseling.
Willingness to Participate in the Study	Teachers must voluntarily agree to participate, provide informed consent, and be open to sharing their professional experiences and observations regarding the research topic.
Employment in Schools with High Social Media Exposure	Teachers should be employed in schools where students have significant access to social media, either through personal devices or school technology integration, to ensure relevant insights.

Sampling Technique

During the conduct of this study, a Purposive Sampling Technique was intentionally utilized to carefully select the young learners in DepEd East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025,, who meet the specific inclusion criteria established by the researcher.

Purposive sampling, alternately referred to as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, constitutes a variant of non-probability sampling. Within this approach, researchers exercise their own judgment and discretionary acumen in the selection of individuals from the population to partake in their survey endeavors (Alchemer, 2021). This method of sampling mandates that researchers possess prior knowledge of the objectives underpinning their study so as to effectively pinpoint and make contact with eligible participants through online survey platforms like Alchemer. Researchers resort to

purposive sampling in order to secure access to a distinct subgroup of individuals, whereby all survey respondents are meticulously chosen based on their alignment with a specific demographic or criterion.

Research Instruments

The researcher in this qualitative study used a semi-structured interview as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). Its purpose is to facilitate an in-depth exploration of the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025.

Data Gathering Procedure

In the initial phase, the researcher diligently sought formal authorization from both the Superintendent of DepEd-Tacurong City and the Dean of the College of Graduate Studies (CGS). This authorization was essential to obtain the necessary permissions for the researcher to conduct the study, emphasizing the importance of ethical considerations.

Following this, a secondary authorization letter was sent to the District Supervisor, explicitly requesting access to the specific data required for this research. A meticulously crafted survey questionnaire was developed, subjected to rigorous evaluation, and then administered to the targeted participants.

The researcher employed a Purposive Sampling Technique to carefully select secondary school teachers as participants in this study. Assuming strict adherence to established health protocols, the researcher proceeded with conducting interviews and facilitating Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), all of which were conducted through face-to-face interactions.

Ultimately, the data collected from interviews and FGDs were systematically organized, subjected to comprehensive analysis, and interpreted using the thematic analysis approach. This approach was expected to provide a deeper understanding of the issues under investigation.

Data Transcription Process

All gathered raw data from the participants through interviews and FGDs were transcribed using the transcription process of Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). By following these step-by-step processes, the researcher aligned the transcription approach with the guidelines outlined by Kvale and Brinkmann (2009). This rigorous transcription process ensured the trustworthiness and credibility of the qualitative data, which served as the foundation for the subsequent phenomenological analysis and the meaningful interpretation of the gathered raw data.

In the context of the study on the socio-emotional well-being of young learners exposed to social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, the steps in the transcription process were outlined as follows:

Step 1: Audio Recording of Interviews: The first step in the transcription process involved audio recording interviews with the participants. For this study, the researcher conducted in-depth interviews with young learners who regularly used social media platforms in schools across East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat. These interviews were recorded with explicit consent from the participants.

Step 2: Verbatim Transcription: Verbatim transcription was crucial as it captured participants' responses exactly as spoken, including pauses, hesitations, and emotional expressions. The researcher meticulously transcribed the audio recordings, ensuring to preserve the precise language, grammatical structures, and speech patterns of the young learners interviewed.

Step 3: Researcher Verification: After transcription, the researcher verified the accuracy of the transcripts by carefully reviewing them for any discrepancies or omissions. This step ensured that the written text faithfully represented the original audio recordings and maintained the integrity of the data collected.

Step 4: Participant Validation: Following transcription, the researcher shared the transcripts with participants for their review and feedback. Participants had the opportunity to validate the accuracy of their recorded responses, providing insights or clarifications where necessary. This process ensured that participants' perspectives were accurately represented in the study.

Step 5: Anonymization: To protect participants' confidentiality, the researcher anonymized transcripts by replacing any identifying information, such as names or specific locations, with pseudonyms or generic descriptors. This precautionary measure safeguarded the privacy of young learners involved in the study.

Data Analysis

In the context of the study on the socio-emotional well-being of young learners exposed to social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, a case study analysis employed a thematic analysis approach to examine the collected data. This methodology, as articulated by Flick (2014), involved systematically categorizing textual components such as statements, phrases, and words into organized groupings or categories. These categories were either derived from established frameworks or custom-developed to align with the study's specific objectives.

To execute this analytical process, a series of essential steps were diligently followed:

Initially, all data sources, including interview transcripts, notes from Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), and relevant documents, were meticulously organized and prepared for analysis. This phase ensured the systematic arrangement and accessibility of the data.

Subsequently, the researchers deeply engaged with the data by conducting a thorough review of interview transcripts and FGD notes. This immersive process aided in gaining a comprehensive understanding of the content and context embedded within the collected information.

The third step involved initiating a systematic coding process. Initial codes were generated by identifying meaningful segments or patterns within the data, capturing essential concepts, ideas, or themes related to the socio-emotional impacts of social media use among young learners.

Following coding, the identified codes were grouped into preliminary themes based on shared meaning or relevance. This step aimed to establish an initial structure for organizing the data and exploring the socio-emotional implications of social media exposure.

Next, the emerging themes and their corresponding codes underwent a process of review and refinement. Researchers ensured the consistency and clarity of these themes, making necessary adjustments as they interpreted the data in the context of young learners' socio-emotional well-being.

Relevant data excerpts, such as quotes or segments extracted from interviews and FGDs, were selected and associated with the respective themes. These excerpts served as supporting evidence for the identified themes, enhancing the credibility and depth of the analysis.

Finally, the thematic analysis extended beyond surface-level identification. Researchers interpreted the meaning and implications of each theme within the context of the study's objectives. They sought patterns, connections, and variations within the themes to provide a comprehensive understanding of the socio-emotional challenges faced by young learners exposed to social media platforms.

This meticulous and structured process of thematic analysis enabled researchers to systematically explore and comprehend the socio-emotional impacts of social media exposure among young learners in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat. Ultimately, this approach yielded valuable insights that contributed to the development of educational strategies and interventions aimed at promoting positive socio-emotional development among young learners in the digital age.

Scope and Delimitation

This study aims to explore the socio-emotional well-being of young learners in the East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, who are exposed to various social media

platforms. The focus was on understanding the impact of social media usage on aspects such as emotional stability, social interactions, self-esteem, and overall mental health.

The study is limited to young learners in the East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat. Findings may not be generalizable to other regions or districts. The study focused on young learners aged 10-15 years old. Younger children and older adolescents are not included in this study. - Due to the nature of a case study analysis, the sample size may be relatively small, focusing on a select group of learners for an in-depth understanding rather than a large-scale survey. Data were collected through interviews, and focus group discussions with students, parents, and teachers. Observational data may also be included.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In recent years, the proliferation of social media platforms has significantly influenced various aspects of individuals' lives, including the socio-emotional well-being of young learners. As digital natives, young learners are increasingly exposed to social media platforms from an early age, shaping their interactions, perceptions, and behaviors both online and offline. In this study, a qualitative research, specifically the a multiple-case study, was employed to explore deeply the socio-emotional well-being of young learners as influenced by their exposure to different social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025. The study involved a total of 15 teachers in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat province during the school year 2024-2025, who meet the researcher's specified inclusion criteria. The researcher in this qualitative study used a semi-structured interview as an investigative instrument during both in-depth interviews and Focus Group Discussions (FGDs). This study employed a thematic analysis approach to examine the collected data.

Result shows that the experiences and interactions of young learners with social media in East-Tacurong District highlight the complex role digital platforms play in shaping their socio-emotional well-being. Social media can be a source of connection, validation, and emotional support, but it also exposes young learners to risks such as social comparison, cyberbullying, and excessive screen time. To navigate these challenges, guidance from parents, teachers, and mentors is essential to ensure that young learners use social media in a balanced and healthy way. As the digital world continues to evolve, it is crucial to provide young learners with the tools they need to maintain their emotional health and well-being in the face of these digital influences.

Further, the socio-emotional challenges faced by young learners due to their exposure to social media are both diverse and profound. As illustrated by the themes discussed above, young learners are vulnerable to a range of emotional difficulties, including cyberbullying, social comparison, addiction, disrupted social development, and mental health struggles. These challenges highlight the need for digital literacy programs, parental guidance, and the promotion of healthy online habits to mitigate the negative impacts of social media. Recent research underscores the importance of addressing

these issues proactively to support the emotional and psychological well-being of young learners in an increasingly digital world.

Furthermore, young learners employ various coping strategies to navigate the challenges associated with social media use. By engaging in open communication with parents, seeking support from trusted individuals, setting boundaries, participating in offline activities, developing digital literacy, building confidence, prioritizing self-care, and limiting social comparison, they cultivate resilience and maintain a healthier relationship with digital platforms. Future research should explore how educational institutions and policymakers can further support young learners in developing these coping skills in an increasingly digital world.

Finally, result reveals that while social media poses certain risks, its potential benefits for the socio-emotional development of young learners cannot be overlooked. By fostering social connections, promoting self-expression, enhancing communication skills, providing emotional support, increasing cultural awareness, facilitating learning, encouraging emotional regulation, strengthening family bonds, and supporting career exploration, social media plays a vital role in shaping young individuals. However, responsible and guided use is necessary to maximize these benefits while mitigating potential drawbacks. With proper digital literacy education and parental guidance, young learners can harness the positive aspects of social media to enhance their overall well-being and development.

Conclusions

The following inferences were made in light of this study's findings:

The experiences of young learners in East-Tacurong District underscore the dual impact of social media—offering connection and support while also posing risks such as social comparison and cyberbullying. Ensuring a balanced and healthy digital experience requires active guidance from parents, teachers, and mentors.

The socio-emotional difficulties young learners face, including cyberbullying, addiction, and mental health concerns, emphasize the need for digital literacy programs and structured parental involvement. Proactively addressing these issues is vital in safeguarding their emotional well-being in the digital era.

Young learners develop resilience by employing coping strategies such as open communication, self-discipline, offline engagement, and digital literacy. Future research should focus on how educational institutions and policymakers can further support these adaptive strategies.

While social media presents certain risks, its benefits—such as fostering connections, promoting self-expression, and enhancing communication—are invaluable. To maximize these advantages, responsible usage through digital literacy education and parental guidance is essential for young learners' socio-emotional growth.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the following were recommended:

1. DepEd and District Supervisors:

- **Implement Digital Literacy Programs:** Incorporate digital literacy into the curriculum at all grade levels to help students develop critical thinking skills and navigate the risks and opportunities of social media. These programs should cover safe online behavior, identifying cyberbullying, and managing online privacy.
- **Strengthen Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) Initiatives:** Integrate social-emotional learning (SEL) in the curriculum to help students build resilience, self-awareness, and emotional regulation. This will empower learners to better cope with the challenges associated with social media.
- **Support Teacher Training:** Provide ongoing professional development for teachers on how to address socio-emotional well-being in the digital age, focusing on identifying and managing the psychological effects of social media use.
- **Create Clear Policies on Social Media Use:** Develop school-wide guidelines and policies that promote healthy online habits and set boundaries for social media engagement during school hours, while encouraging students to balance screen time with offline activities.

2. School Administrators:

- **Promote Parental Involvement:** Engage parents through workshops or communication campaigns to educate them on the impact of social media on their children's socio-emotional well-being and offer tips on monitoring usage, setting screen time limits, and fostering open communication.
- **Offer Counseling Services:** Establish a robust support system with trained counselors who can help students navigate issues like cyberbullying, social comparison, and mental health struggles related to social media exposure. Provide individual and group counseling to strengthen emotional resilience.
- **Organize Awareness Campaigns:** Coordinate initiatives that raise awareness about the positive and negative impacts of social media. These campaigns can include interactive discussions, student presentations, and peer mentorship programs to create an open dialogue about social media use and mental health.

3. Teachers:

- **Encourage Healthy Coping Strategies:** Help students develop and implement coping strategies such as limiting social media use, engaging in offline activities, and practicing self-care. Reinforce the importance of maintaining face-to-face relationships and prioritizing in-person socialization.
- **Foster Open Communication:** Create a classroom environment that encourages students to talk openly about their experiences with social media, providing them with a safe space to share concerns and seek guidance. Facilitate discussions around the emotional impact of social media.
- **Guide Students in Setting Boundaries:** Educate students on how to set healthy boundaries when it comes to screen time and social media engagement.

Encourage them to create schedules that balance online and offline activities, and monitor their emotional responses to digital interactions.

4. Future Researchers:

- **Investigate the Role of Digital Literacy:** Explore the effectiveness of digital literacy programs in reducing the negative emotional impacts of social media on young learners. Research how these programs can be tailored to different age groups and learning needs.
- **Examine the Influence of Parental Guidance:** Study the role of parental involvement and guidance in shaping how children use social media. Investigate the specific strategies that parents can adopt to mitigate risks and promote healthy online habits.
- **Explore Coping Mechanisms:** Further research how young learners develop and utilize coping mechanisms to deal with the emotional challenges posed by social media. This can include studies on self-regulation, social support systems, and the role of offline activities in balancing digital experiences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for conducting the study on the socio-emotional well-being of young learners exposed to social media platforms in East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, all proposed plans and recommendations were formally presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc. to ensure adherence to prescribed procedures and protocols. Within the context of this research, which focused on exploring the lived experiences of young learners, it was crucial to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations. Prior to commencing this study during the school year 2024-2025, the following ethical principles were meticulously observed:

Informed Consent: Explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all parents or guardians of participating students. They were fully informed about the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Participation was voluntary, and participants had the autonomy to withdraw at any time without consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality: To protect the identities and responses of participants, stringent measures were implemented to maintain anonymity and confidentiality. Pseudonyms or codes were used instead of actual names, and all collected data were securely stored with limited access restricted to the research team.

Avoiding Harm: Sensitive topics related to socio-emotional well-being and social media exposure were handled with careful consideration for potential emotional and psychological impacts on participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and support services were readily accessible as needed (Magonsik & Ngag, 2025).

Researcher-Participant Relationship: The researcher maintained a professional and respectful relationship with all participants, ensuring their dignity and well-being

throughout the research process. Actions that could exploit or harm participants were strictly avoided.

Data Protection: Stringent adherence to data protection regulations was upheld to safeguard all personal information collected during the study. Secure storage and transmission protocols were implemented to prevent unauthorized access.

Voluntary Participation: Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was voluntary and free from coercion or external pressure (Dolutan & Ngag, 2024).

Researcher Bias: The researcher remained vigilant against biases that could influence data collection and analysis, promoting objectivity and transparency in reporting findings (Ronquillo & Ngag, 2024)..

Institutional Approval: Ethical clearance was sought from relevant institutional review boards or ethics committees prior to initiating the study.

Honesty and Integrity: Research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, without manipulation or distortion, to uphold the integrity of the study.

Beneficence:

Potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were carefully considered, aiming to contribute positively to the enhancement of the education system (Ngag, 2023).

Cultural Sensitivity: The researcher demonstrated cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, avoiding imposition of external values on participants.

Inclusion and Diversity: The study prioritized inclusivity and diversity in participant selection, aiming to encompass a broad spectrum of young learners' experiences with social media in East-Tacurong District. By meticulously adhering to these ethical considerations, the research was conducted responsibly and respectfully, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the young learners involved (Bantillo & Ngag, 2024). Simultaneously, it provided valuable insights into the socio-emotional impacts of social media use within the specific educational context of East-Tacurong District, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2024-2025.

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REFERENCES

- Alchemer. (2021). *Survey Sampling Methods*. Retrieved from <https://www.alchemer.com>
- Bantillo, R. B., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). CHANGING LANDSCAPE OF FILIPINO EDUCATION: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON TRADITIONAL VS. MODERNIZED APPROACHES TO TEACHING FILIPINO. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(6), 2409–2420. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635314>
- Best, P., Manktelow, R., & Taylor, B. (2014). Online communication, social media and adolescent well-being: A systematic narrative review. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 41, 27-36
- Dolutan, M. N., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CENTENNIAL TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MODERNIZATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN DEPED BAGUMBAYAN DISTRICT III. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.17613/n5qw-6920>
- Flick, U. (2014). *An introduction to qualitative research* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Magonsik, R. W., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2025). UNVEILING TEACHERS' MOTIVATION OF LEAVING DEPED TO TEACH ABROAD: A NARRATIVE INQUIRY. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(2), 791–806. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14948796>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Unveiling The Literary Appreciation of Teduray Students: A Case Study Analysis of Their Works. *Boletin De Literatura Oral - Tradition Oral Literature*, 10(1), 30-3. <http://boletindeliteratuoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/5>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Efficacy of Téduray Literature Module in Teaching English. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 404–409. <https://doi.org/10.57030/23364890.cemj.31.1.3>
- Ronquillo, K. C., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). OVERCOMING LINGUISTIC HURDLES: INVESTIGATING CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MAGUINDANAON STUDENTS IN ACHIEVING PROFICIENCY IN SPEAKING ENGLISH. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133747>
- Twenge, J. M., & Campbell, W. K. (2018). Associations between screen time and lower psychological well-being among children and adolescents: Evidence from a population-based study. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 12, 271-283
- Viner, R. M, Bonell, C., & Hargreaves, D. S. (2019). Roles of social media in adolescent mental health: A review. *The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health*, 3(3), 157-167. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642\(18\)30092-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2352-4642(18)30092-9)